

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF LOGISTICS SERVICES IN THE TEXTILE INDUSTRY

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In modern conditions of the global market, with the peculiarities of globalization and increased competition, manufacturing enterprises should strive not only to meet the needs of their domestic market, but also to develop large international markets through exports. Achieving a competitive advantage in the international arena requires the development and implementation of an effective operational strategy in the production of export-oriented products.

The operational strategy in production is a systematic and integrated approach to business process management aimed at achieving a high level of efficiency and competitiveness of the enterprise. The main objectives of the strategy include optimizing production processes, reducing production cycle time, improving product quality, reducing costs and minimizing risks.

When developing an operational strategy for the production of export-oriented products, it is necessary to take into account a number of key factors. First, it is the analysis and study of international markets and consumer demand. It is necessary to understand the characteristics and advantages of the target markets, as well as the requirements for quality, price and service. Secondly, the strategy should include optimization of logistics processes, including warehouse organization, transportation and supply chain management. Thirdly, the improvement of the operational strategy also involves automation and the introduction of innovative technologies to improve the efficiency of production processes.

In addition, an important aspect is the development of a supplier management strategy to ensure reliable and high-quality supplies of components and raw

materials. The strategy should also take into account the possibility of expanding production and scaling up the enterprise to meet export demand.

The operational strategy in the production of export-oriented products is a complex and multifaceted process that requires analysis, planning and implementation of many factors and strategic decisions. However, its successful implementation allows the company to create a solid foundation for development in international markets, which provides a competitive advantage and sustainable growth.

In the process of preparing the thesis, general scientific, formal-logical, specific methods of studying the situation were used, such as system analysis, classification, generalization, horizontal and vertical analysis, econometric modeling, factor analysis, correlation and regression analysis, economic analysis and forecasting.

A number of large retail stores and clothing brands of the European Union are considering the possibility of cooperation with Uzbek textile companies.

Uzbekistan, unlike other global manufacturers, has great advantages:

availability of an existing value-added textile production chain;

Due to the proximity to the European continent, logistics channels are available (fast delivery time).

In addition, Uzbekistan can become a new manufacturer and a state with a special vision in the field of fashion and design.

Exports of textile products to the Ferghana region in January-July 2024 amounted to 168.3 million US dollars, which is 35.9% of total exports, an increase of 2.7% compared to last year. Since the beginning of the year, 135 types of textiles have been exported to 43 countries around the world.

- As part of exported textiles
- Cotton yarn -110.3 million US dollars
- Knitted fabric -7.3 million US dollars
- Ready-made knitted and sewing clothes -31.9 million US dollars.

Logistics develops and complements marketing by linking supplier, manufacturer, consumer (and transport) into a mobile, organizational, technological, and planned-economic coordinated business system. Marketing tracks and

determines demand, that is, it answers the questions: what kind of product is needed, where, when, in what quantity and in what quality. Logistics ensures the physical promotion of the required form of flow to the consumer and allows the consumer to deliver the required amount of goods to the right place at the right time with minimal cost. Marketing sets itself the task of a systematic approach to the organization of the movement of goods, with the effective organization of the movement of goods, each stage of this process should be planned as an integral part of a balanced and logically constructed overall system. In this regard, the methods of organizational and technological integration of all participants in the movement of goods are the main subject of logistics study.

Commerce implies the process of organizational, technical and socio-economic interaction of market participants in the distribution and organization of the exchange of goods and services on an equivalent basis. The main object of commercial logistics is the material flow, which cannot be optimized and rationalized without coordination with the relevant flows: financial, service, information. As a result, commercial logistics defines a flow management system related to the purchase and distribution of goods to achieve reliability and flexibility of production and trade.

At the same time, market development and changes and dynamics of market processes determine the specifics of economic relations occurring in logistics systems, which allows coordinated management of flow processes, ensuring their synchronicity and synergetic integration, leading to significant end results for all participants.

The variety of logistics processes makes it possible to integrate components of logistics systems, as well as use a number of approaches to achieve the most accurate and meaningful results in accordance with the goals and objectives of business entities, taking into account differences in the working conditions of enterprises and even similar departments.

Ensuring high and sustainable growth rates of the textile and clothing and knitwear industry of the republic, attracting and developing foreign direct investment, manufacturing and exporting competitive products, creating new high-tech jobs through the implementation of strategically important modernization projects, technical and technological renewal of enterprises, the introduction of a progressive "cluster model" systematic work is being carried out to further deepen

structural reorganization aimed at the introduction of new technologies. In particular, Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 5, 2020 No. PF-5989 "On urgent measures to support the textile and clothing and knitwear industry" and Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 16, 2019 No. PF-5989 "on measures to further develop light industry and stimulate the production of finished products" Decision No. PP-4453 is proof of the consistent implementation in our country of practical measures aimed at ensuring the further development of this area. At the same time, a comprehensive analysis of the development of the textile and clothing and knitwear industries, the changing global market conditions in the face of increased competition require the development and implementation of mechanisms for state support of the industry, as well as its more sustainable and dynamic development. The weight of knitwear increases regularly. This is due to the high serviceability and cost-effectiveness of knitwear¹.

In the first two months of 2022, Uzbekistan exported about 8 thousand tons of knitwear worth 45.6 million US dollars to 15 foreign countries. The volume of exports of knitwear increased by 8.4 million US dollars compared to the corresponding period last year. The countries that exported the largest amount of Uzbek knitwear during this period: Russia - 14.5 million, Kyrgyzstan - 14.2 million, Italy - 8.6 million, Ukraine - 2.8 million US dollars².

Tashkent city - 19.1 million, Tashkent region - 9.1 million, Andijan region - 6.4 million, Bukhara region - 3 million US dollars.

As a result of many years of efforts to further deepen the ongoing reforms in the textile and clothing and knitwear industries, create favorable conditions for accelerated development and diversification of the industry, increase investments in deep processing of textile semi-finished products and exports of finished products:

- The Concept of accelerated development of the textile and clothing and knitwear industry for 2019-2025 has been approved

- expenses related to the payment of interest on loans from commercial banks to sewing and knitting enterprises exporting at least 80% of finished products are

¹ Курпаяниди, К.И. (2022). Факторы и направления развития институтов в сфере малого предпринимательства. Проблемы современной экономики, 3 (83).

² www. Stat.uz/uz/ sanoat

covered by the state fund for support of business development under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan

- strict bank guarantees for the sale of cotton fiber through stock trading have been canceled

- the value added tax is calculated based on the actual selling price of cotton fiber, regardless of the prices formed on world markets

- to increase the volume of exports of textile products to 7 billion US dollars by 2025 by processing the entire volume of cotton yarn produced in the republic

- The Uzstandard Agency, together with the Uztextilsanoat Association, to conduct a census of existing regulatory legal acts on standards that establish requirements for textile and clothing and knitwear industry products for their testing methods, and to establish standards that are subject to revision taking into account international norms.

Conclusion. Thus, logistics contributes to the coordination of functional areas of economic activity, optimization of the management system and stability of production and market positions of economic structures. In conclusion, it should be said that with the deepening of reforms aimed at the development of the textile and clothing and knitwear industries, and ensuring the need for qualified personnel in the textile industry, the quality of manufacturing a wide range of high-quality textiles in the country will increase, which will lead to further improvement of the welfare of our people.

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